

Novel Documentation and Identification Methods for Combating Illicit Trafficking of Cultural Goods - ENIGMA Pilot Case Studies

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Abstract: The EU-funded ENIGMA project develops innovative methods and tools to enhance cultural heritage safeguarding, protection, and provenance management, specifically targeting the illicit trafficking of cultural goods. This paper presents two initial pilot case studies that evaluate and validate the project's developments. Pilot Case 1 focuses on novel documentation of museum items using the Unique Authenticity Identifier to improve traceability. Pilot Case 2 investigates the identification and tracking of unregistered cultural goods by employing advanced technologies and AI to uncover connections with known inventoried objects. The pilots scrutinize operational scenarios, user profiles, and initial object selection consisting of figurines from the Royal Museums of Art and History (KMG). Preliminary findings suggest ENIGMA tools demonstrate their potential as a prototype solution, with resilient and adaptable workflows for various user groups. Future work includes integrating the complete tool suite into the ENIGMA Decision Support Platform and implementing further pilot cases.

1. Introduction

The EU-funded project ENIGMA “Endorsing safeguarding, protection & provenance management of cultural heritage” under GA 101094237 [PG23] is developing novel cultural goods documentation methods, and a set of tools as part of the ENIGMA platform to help in the fight against the illicit trafficking of cultural goods (CGs). To evaluate and validate the developed methodologies, tools, and the integrated platform, the project will implement four pilot case studies. Hence, this publication presents the design along with the scope of two pilot cases. More specifically the pilot case 1 “Novel documentation of museum items”, and pilot case 2 “Identification and tracking of unregistered cultural goods” are going to be analyzed.

2. Pilot case description

2.1. Pilot case 1 “Novel documentation of museum items”

The main objective of the 1st pilot case is to investigate methods that will enhance the traceability of museum items by introducing and validating novel ways of documentation. Currently investigating the provenance, origin, or authenticity of CGs is based on a minimum amount of information, which create barriers to trace them. The ENIGMA project introduced the concept of the Unique Authenticity Identifier (UAI), that provides protocols on data requirements for proper authentication and can be scaled across diverse cultural contexts. Pilot case 1 will validate the efficiency and efficacy of the proposed workflow. Furthermore, it will evaluate the application of different practices / strategies according to each host’s regulations and procedures.

It has been observed that the most dominant cases of smuggled objects in Europe and worldwide are small items [INT20, INT21]. As a result, museum items offer a typical sample of the most important test cases. The ENIGMA end user partners will test, validate and evaluate the developed novel concepts by documenting several of their CGS using the proposed techniques and methodologies. The selected items will cover a wide range of 2D / 3D types, dimensions, physical / material / structural peculiarities and complexities as well as data formats and metadata. The latter will also be used to validate the portability of the information across the current databases / inventories.

2.2. Pilot case 2 “Identification and tracking of unregistered cultural goods”

A major bottleneck / barrier in the identification of CGs is that the available technologies and methodologies presuppose that a CG is known, documented and registered. However, the typical case in looting and smuggling is that the items being trafficked are unknown, unregistered and undocumented. ENIGMA tackles this issue by using advanced technologies and AI techniques to uncover possible connections of an unknown CG to known inventoried objects. The main objective of the 2nd pilot case is to validate the efficiency and efficacy of the proposed workflow by using real life scenarios and cultural goods. Furthermore, it will also evaluate the application of different practices / strategies considering the ethical issues associated with each end user regulation and procedures.

ENIGMA’s end user partners will provide test cases coming from the results of the 1st pilot case based on the defined scenario schemes. This test cases will also include metadata from external repositories regarding known inventoried CGs under investigation. The identification of the unregistered CGs will be accomplished by exploring contextual relations of CG annotation and the developed methodologies and tools for exploring the project’s database. The validation of the integrity of the results will be checked against known museum items.

3. Documentation of cultural objects

One of the most common standards used on the documentation of CGs at museums is Getty’s Object ID™ [ICO99, GET99]. Getty’s Object ID™ is an internationally recognized documentation standard conceived to identify and record cultural goods. It defines 9 categories of information and 4 steps to realize the procedure. The categories of information are: 1) Type of object, 2) Materials and techniques, 3) Measurements, 4) Inscriptions and markings, 5) Distinguishing features, 6) Title, 7) Subject, 8) Date or period, and 9) Maker. While the required steps are: 1) Taking photographs of the object, 2) Identifying the mentioned categories, 3) Writing a short description, including additional information, and 4) Keeping the constituted documentation in a secure place. If the cultural

good is registered this information is available, if the information is unknown, it should be entered on the spot.

3.1. Current KMKG documentation practices

The Royal Museums of Art and History (Koninklijke Musea voor Kunst en Geschiedenis, KMKG), Brussels, manage a varied quantity of collections. The museum presents a significant collections ranging from Art Nouveau and medieval manuscripts to furniture from 16-20th century and overseas collections from China, India, South East Asia, Islam, among others. This article concentrates on collections from Mesopotamia, Greece and Ancient Rome, as objects from these civilisations closely relate to the issues that ENIGMA addresses.

This section describes the current registration practices for archaeological material within the KMKG but may vary according to the type of collection due to the versatility of the collections. Archaeological practices have changed significantly over the past decades, with tighter legislation in the countries where the research is performed and, in general, changes in approaches and policies towards the materials recovered, implying that these materials remain in their respective countries of origin.

The practices presented here are based on archaeological material discovered mainly in the 20th century. Since 2006, KMKG has put a Collection Management System (CMS) in place to manage its inventory and collections. The CMS is partially adapted per collection in order to document the collections' particularities effectively. With regard to archaeological collections, provenance and location is of utmost importance. This type of information is usually laid down in excavation and research reports which give precise information on objects, their site location, and their relation. Information from these reports is compiled on a higher, less detailed level in the CMS. Whenever possible, links to the original documentation are included in the CMS records.

As the CMS is central to all KMKG operations, including the museums' inventory maintenance and exchanges with other online resources, a high level of compliance to international standards is assured. The CMS can export metadata for Conversion to EDM, the Europeana Data Model (EDM). KMKG uses the Getty suite of documentation tools, such as the Art & Architecture Thesaurus (AAT) for object names, and the Getty Thesaurus of Geographic Names (TGN) for geographic references. The AAT is slightly adapted to the specific museums collections' needs. Further, standard documentation fields are applied like materials, dimensions, date (where also different time systems are included, e.g., the Egyptian Pharaonic dynasties), author/culture, location in the museum. Outstanding archaeological artefacts are photographed, occasionally other capture methods like 3D or multispectral imaging are used. Details of further studies – in separate reports – are linked to the CMS.

3.2. ENIGMA's documentation approach

The ENIGMA project created a joint workspace in order to integrate data from multiple sources. The core of the workspace is a relational database based on EDM. The unified relational schema incorporated the EDM and CIDOC CRM schemas including information from the Dublin Core Metadata initiative to create ENIGMA's relational database schema to support the documentation of unknown / unregistered objects. Furthermore, to standardize the recording of cultural goods and provide a structured authoritative terminology for cultural goods documentation the following Getty vocabularies were used: AAT, the Union List of Artist Names (ULAN), and TGN. The use of

these vocabularies ensures consistency in data entry and accurate metadata linking that are essential for trustworthy provenance research.

3.3. ENIGMA's UAI

ENIGMA's UAI [PRG25] aims to identify unregistered and undocumented cultural goods by extending the Object ID™ and using AI and machine learning tools to provide insights into their provenance. Feature categorization in the UAI is based on a 3-tier data classification scheme. The first tier contains the primary parameters (Subject, Type of object, Materials & techniques, Dimensions, including weight, Object photos, Inscriptions & markings, Distinguishing features). The second tier contains the secondary parameters (Content semantics, Textual content, Historical context, Spatial/Location associations). The third tier contains the optimum/miscellaneous parameters (3D, image, and surface/texture characteristics).

4. Initial pilot scenarios

Pilot 1, "Novel Documentation of Museum Items," and Pilot 2, "Identification and Tracking of Unregistered Cultural Goods," simulate real-world situations as testing grounds for the developed tools and workflows. The pilots are interrelated, using the same object input, consisting of small historic artefacts - specifically figurines, complement one another, and which are detailed below.

Pilot 1 Operational Scenario: The main objective of this pilot is to investigate methods to enhance the authenticity and traceability of museum items by introducing and validating novel documentation approaches. Users will input detailed and accurate cultural goods (CG) information into the provenance research tool interface for the retrieval of cultural heritage goods from the ENIGMA database. The steps of data entry, retrieval, and validation will be undertaken and assessed.

Pilot 2 Operational Scenario: The main objective of Pilot 2 is to validate the efficiency and efficacy of the proposed workflow through scenario building using real museum items (as documented in Pilot 1). A user is confronted with an object, and the provenance research tool, utilizing the UAI, supports the identification and provenance determination of the object. Both pilots are developed for the following target user profiles:

- User 1: Law Enforcement Agency (LEA) officers, Border officers
- User 2: Experienced LEA officers, Experienced Border officers
- User 3: Archaeologists, Museum experts/curators, Ministry of Culture representatives

Specific interfaces and datasets are prepared for each user profile. The functionality and services offered by the interfaces depend on the user's profile and the situation in which the UAI is created or utilized. These user profiles are consistent across both Pilot 1 and Pilot 2.

4.1 Pilot case 1

Pilot Case 1 begins with the following operational scenario: "A user enters detailed and accurate CG information into the provenance research tool utilizing the UAI for the retrieval of cultural heritage goods from the ENIGMA database."

The scenario gathers information of each artefact. Each artefact is registered in the museum database, including metadata,

provenance descriptions, and 2D visual inputs (e.g., photographs). Additionally, 3D digitization of the figurines is initiated to validate the 3D reconstruction tool and check for similarities within the ENIGMA system. The ENIGMA platform allows users to select information such as artefact categories, dimensions, and materials based on AAT.

This pilot tests the interaction between different user profiles and the interface, as well as the workflow for data entry and retrieval. Through iterative interaction, such as entering information and evaluating results, ENIGMA seeks to establish an optimal balance between data acquisition effort and UAI effectiveness. The UAI is a flexible set of data that contributes to the identification and provenance of CGs, allowing inputs from minimal to highly detailed information. The more information the UAI contains, the more detailed and accurate the identification of the object will be.

This pilot will test both data entry and data retrieval. The primary goal of pilot case 1 is to assess the easiness of data acquisition for the optimized documentation of a CG, the acceptance of the acquisition workflow by the stakeholders, and the effectiveness of the developed tools. For User-2 and 3, ENIGMA will provide a standard interface for alphanumeric data entry and accompanying files. In addition, it will support the creation of hierarchical data structures. The use of internationally recognized vocabularies, such as AAT and TGN, will be explored within the UAI. The following steps are envisaged during the implementation:

1. Enter digital text information into the Provenance research tool.
2. Add 2D imaging to the Provenance research tool application.
3. Create a 3D model of the CG and insert it into the database.
4. Based on CG features, the system retrieves a list of similar objects.
5. The user reviews and amends the record, including all relevant information. The record may be referred to colleague specialists for supplementary information.
6. The UAI record is established.

Data retrieval operations will primarily involve interface-based data management, including access to standard vocabularies. ENIGMA proposes a structured workflow for data entry based on available object data (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: Proposed workflow for Pilot Case 1.

4.2 Pilot case 2

Building on information from Pilot 1, Pilot 2 focuses on adding provenance data to determine whether an item is looted or illegally trafficked and to provide basic provenance information where possible. Since looted and smuggled items are typically undocumented, ENIGMA addresses this by applying AI techniques to uncover potential links between unknown seized CGs and known inventoried CGs.

Since authentic museum objects cannot be transferred to LEA officers, a series of cast objects (as reproductions or alleged forgeries) have been created for validation purposes. Like Pilot 1, Pilot 2 uses a scenario-based approach: "A user (e.g., one of the three target users) is confronted with an object. The ENIGMA platform supports the identification and provenance determination of the object." As a starting point, users answer a set of questions regarding the object to determine its identity, provenance, and authenticity, and to assess the legality of its transport. These questions could consist of the following:

Documentation:

1. Is there accompanying documentation with the object?
2. What does the documentation consist of?
3. Is the documentation complete and comprehensive?
4. Is the documentation reliable?
5. Can the owner of the object be established?
6. Can the destination of the object be established?

Further object information:

1. Establish the object identity: What is it?
2. Establish the object provenance: Where does it come from?
3. Establish the object authenticity: Is it authentic/original?
4. Is the provenance (documentation) reliable?

By addressing the above set of questions, and based on oral and written evidence, the user can then reflect on the general question: Is this transport legal? A proposed workflow visualizes how LEA officers engage with archaeologists and museum experts to determine the status of a potentially looted or illegally trafficked CG (Fig. 2). In addition, the user will enter the basic descriptive information in the ENIGMA platform and assign the identification to an expert. The expert consequently will use the provenance research tool based on the UAI in order to establish the origin / provenance of the CG and decide if it is legally or illegally transported.

Figure 2: Proposed workflow for Pilot Case 2.

4.3 Initial object selection for the pilots

The initial pilot test objects consist of nine figurines stemming from the KMKG collections and the KMKG plaster cast workshop [KMK25]. The plaster casts are created by using traditional molding and patina techniques, faithfully resembling originals to simulate looted items as closely as possible. The selected figurines correspond to ENIGMA's emphasis on Mediterranean antiquities, primarily from Ancient Egypt, Greece, and the Ancient Near East. The figurines and their casts are listed in the KMKG catalogues including Carmentis [KC25]. The specific figurines consist of the following (Fig. 3):

1. Head of a Scorpion Man, Near East, 9thc BC, plaster cast white
2. Akhenaten Mask, Ancient Egypt, 18th Dynasty, plaster cast white
3. Ushebti of Neferenpet, Ancient Egypt, 19th Dynasty, New Kingdom, plaster cast white
4. Ushebti of Neferenpet, Ancient Egypt, 19th Dynasty, New Kingdom, plaster cast patina
5. Amorgos, cycladic statue, Ancient Greece, 4th millennium BC plaster cast patina
6. Scarab of Amenhotep III, Ancient Egypt, Amenhotep III, New Kingdom, plaster cast patina
7. Moai Statue, Easter Island, s.d., plaster cast white
8. Broken Ear, Chimú, Latin America, 1100-1450 AD, plaster cast white
9. Tanagra, Titeux dancer, Ancient Greece, c. 350 BC, plaster cast white

Figure 3: Overview of the Figures used for the Pilot Cases.

For each figurine, metadata is provided and includes a short iconographic description, Object IDs, inventory numbers for both the casts and the originals, current location, collection details, place of origin, and, where available, approximate dates and dimensions. Further, photographs from the KMKG Digital Asset Management System (DAMS) and 3D photogrammetric reconstructions are also provided.

5. Conclusions / Future work

Testing the ENIGMA tools via Pilot Cases 1 and 2 within a museum environment demonstrated that the tools are suitable for a prototype solution (TRL 5-6). The workflows for each pilot case proved both resilient and flexible, allowing users to input data according to their knowledge and skill without compromising tool efficacy and reliability. Pilot Cases 1 and 2 successfully tested the ENIGMA technologies, including the UAI, provenance tool, and scenario-building functionality. Pilot 1 focused on CG documentation and the efficiency and adaptability of ENIGMA's documentation proposals. In contrast, Pilot 2 focused on identifying and tracing unregistered CGs. The results indicate that user groups comprising LEAs, archaeologists, and museum experts can effectively use the tools.

However, this paper presents only 2 of the 4 planned pilot cases, and a thorough validation of the tools is still required. Moreover, the complete suite of tools and procedures will finally be integrated into the ENIGMA Decision Support Platform, comprising a Decision-Support System, a Communication Platform, and an Advanced Data Management System. Therefore, a comprehensive system assessment and validation of the integrated workflow's efficiency and efficacy is still required.

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